

Transparency, reproducibility, and quality of energy system analyses – A process to improve scientific work

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ABSTRACT

In this article we apply the *transparency checklist* methodology by Cao et al. to a case study to evaluate the degree of transparency in energy system modelling. We use a recent case study conducted by the *Reiner Lemoine Institut* that analyses heat and electricity supply in a German region. An analysis of the questions of the *transparency checklist* indicates that different issues are addressed: transparency, reproducibility and quality. The completed checklist with answers regarding the case study and its supplementing materials shows that a large majority of the transparency (93%) and reproducibility criteria (73%) could be satisfied. However, only a smaller proportion (47%) of the questions categorised as quality criteria could be answered satisfyingly. A total of 31 out of 45 checklist questions are answered (69%). More than half (53%) of all questions were answered in the introduced framework, model and scenario fact sheets on the *OpenEnergyPlatform*. The gaps in answering the checklist (e.g., documenting assumptions, uncertainties, and validations) can be closed by an enhancement of the fact sheets and additional tools like the presented *scenario log*. We conclude that supplementing a final report or study with the presented fact sheets improves good scientific practice significantly while we identified existing weaknesses.

1. Introduction

Energy system analyses and scientific studies are usually realised with different simulation or optimisation models. The outcome is used to shape energy policy and develop measures or even directives and laws. As this affects the general public, policy makers, stakeholders, and scientists demand transparency of the whole process. This includes disclosure of applied assumptions and input data, energy system models, results of the analysed scenarios, conclusions, and discussions that lead to the final recommendations (see Fig. 1).

The general lack of transparency in energy system modelling leads to irreproducible results and the loss of traceability in decision making. This lack of transparency is an important obstacle to the scientific debate on energy system analyses and has been analysed and addressed in different investigations [1,2]. The following literature review shows that the problem of non-transparent modelling and results is being addressed. A profound discussion on the strengths and weaknesses of the existing models and which questions can or cannot be answered by them is hampered, and it contradicts the general requirements of good scientific work. Concrete problems in the scientific field are not ver-

ifiable results, waste of time and resources through double-work, slower application of gained knowledge and thus waste of public funding.

In 2012, the research project *ATEsT* [3] stated in a project report [4]: “Increasing the transparency in support of the EU RD&D policy initiatives was suggested as an overall action.” On a global and European level, representatives of national governments and of civil society respond to this requirement with various measures. A prominent example is the statement on open science of the G8 science ministers [5]. In 2016, the *European Commission* established an *Open Science Policy Platform* [6] and since then demands “open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications” in all *H2020* projects [7]. The German *Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy* established a research network for energy systems analyses in order to improve the transparency of research activities and to promote quality assurance [8]. According to statements from modellers at the conference of the *Energy Modelling Platform for Europe* (EMP-E 2017) [9], comparable networks are in development for Denmark, Italy, and Sweden. A growing number of modellers have become members of the *Open Energy Modelling Initiative* (openmod) [10] where they can discuss and exchange methods and technical subjects of open

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Fig. 1. Transparent modelling concept © Reiner Lemoine Institut | CC BY-SA 4.0.

modelling, transparency, and reproducibility. The *openmod* writes in their manifesto [11]: “We believe that more openness in energy modelling increases transparency and credibility, reduces wasteful double-work and improves overall quality.”

In energy system analysis, there is no standard to refer to in order to prove transparency, but there are standards and methods that have been developed in other research fields that can be adapted. For example, the European *INSPIRE* directive [12] determines the reporting requirements and metadata infrastructure for spatial information. Davison [13] has developed a method for automated capture of experiment context in computational research because he states that “research in diverse scientific domains that rely on numerical computation is too infrequently reproducible.” Hinsen [14] analysed methodologies for a complete publishing of general computer aided research while Boettiger [15] recommends the use and provision of platform-independent environments (e.g., *Docker*) for reproducible research. In biomedical engineering (bioinformatics), global standards and infrastructure for sharing scientific data have been around for some years [16]. Pfenniger [17] specifies the problem in the field of energy system analyses: “Sharing a DNA sequence in an established format is, of course, easier than sharing the unstructured assumptions behind a techno-economic scenario study, for which no standard format exists yet. So the energy community must decide on standards for sharing code, data and assumptions.” As a first collection of necessary attributes for a transparent energy system analysis, Cao et al. [1] have published a *transparency checklist*.

We want to pick up the thread and contribute to a standardisation process of sharing information on energy system analyses. We define reproducibility according to the rules of the *German Research Society* for good scientific practice [18]. It is the ability to obtain the same research results or inferences through independent replication of an experiment. Transparency can thus be seen as a principle and a necessary precondition for reproducible research. From a scientific point of view, both transparency and reproducibility are important or even necessary to evaluate the quality of models, data, and recommendations. The main goal of this article is to document the applicability of existing methods, and open it up for further discussion. The evaluated materials and tools (final report, fact sheets and glossary) as well as the suggestions for improvement were designed through cross-institutional collaboration and expert workshops, which were a fundamental part of the research projects *open_eGo* [19] and *open_FRED* [20]. The same issues concerning the need for transparency are addressed in the European research project *REEEM* [21]. The general framework outlined above leads to the following research questions that we want to address:

1. What is the status-quo of transparency and reproducibility in the selected case study regarding the *transparency checklist*?
2. Which areas of the scientific work need improvements to meet the requirements of the first question?
3. What shape can these improvements take?

2. Methodology

The starting point of this investigation is the *transparency checklist* presented by Cao et al. [1]. The checklist is structured into six sections ‘General Information’, ‘Empirical Data’, ‘Assumptions’, ‘Modelling’, ‘Results’, and ‘Conclusions and Recommendations’. Each section has several sub-items that are formulated as questions. We apply these 45 questions to a case study conducted by the *Reiner Lemoine Institut* and carry out a critical self-observation in order to evaluate the degree of transparency and reproducibility in scientific work. In addition to the published final report of the case study [22], all accompanying materials that are publicly available are assessed. This comprises the compiled assumptions and input data [23] (tagged “oemof_abb”) and, of course, the created energy system model [24] with corresponding fact sheets [25]. The assessment of the interpretation of the results, conclusions, and recommendations is not part of this investigation (see Fig. 1). The figure depicts a simplified modelling concept with an unidirectional data flow and the connection to the fact sheets.

In the above-named research projects [19,20], different transparency methods were developed which are integrated in the *OpenEnergyPlatform* (OEP) [26]. This includes multi-level and linked fact sheets, a shared glossary [27], and the *OpenEnergyDatabase* (OEDB) [23] to store and provide open data. The basic concept and main features of the OEDB will be presented and discussed in a separate article.

The central idea of the fact sheets is to provide an online form to simplify the input of information, to provide a clearly arranged representation of a model, and to facilitate public availability of this information (see Fig. 2). The development process of the fact sheets included a first theoretical evaluation of the *transparency checklist*, the list of open models from the *openmod-wiki* [28], and other existing model descriptions. In two expert workshops and in online discussions, the fact sheets were improved and divided into fact sheets for frameworks, models, and scenarios. Search and filter functionalities of the fact sheets yield huge improvements regarding inter-project communication and intended code reuse. Software developers and policy advisers get an

Fig. 2. UML class diagram of fact sheets © OvGU | CC BY-SA 4.0.

Table 1
Allocation and results of the *transparency checklist* questions per category.

Field	T	Score	R	Score	Q	Score	Total
General Information	6	83%	0	–	2	100%	8 88%
Empirical Data	0	–	2	100%	1	100%	3 100%
Assumptions	3	100%	2	100%	6	33%	11 64%
Model exercise	6	100%	5	80%	3	67%	14 86%
Results	0	–	2	0%	2	50%	4 25%
Conclusions and Recommendations	0	–	0	–	5	20%	5 20%
Sum	15		11		19		45
Mean		93%		73%		47%	69%

overview of existing functionalities and methods, which they can reuse with respect to the corresponding licenses.

Whilst model- and framework fact sheets are rather technical and, apart from the general information, mostly interesting for computer programmers, scenario fact sheets tackle some basic flaws of current scientific energy modelling that are mentioned in the introduction. The information provided illuminates the assumptions that are necessary for specific results. Scenario fact sheets contain information not only on input data and models, but also on adapted model equations and the parameter configuration with which they were used. This can provide an overview of scenarios that are based on similar assumptions, which in turn might allow conclusions on the impact of the sensitivity of results to parameter variations of energy models.

Furthermore, the necessity of a clear and intelligible definition of key terms used in energy system analyses is addressed. In contrast to the separate sections for abbreviations and definitions usually used in each publication, a collective public documentation has been initiated. A shared glossary aims to facilitate the development of a common understanding of terms. This way the different interpretations and applications become apparent and can be discussed openly. In addition to the collected definitions, the glossary contains supplementary information (e.g., abbreviations and sources) and relations (synonyms and subterms). A comparable German equivalent (without being interactive) can be found on the central information system *EnArgus* [29]. Though a glossary is not yet used very widely, it allows to refer to publicly available definitions.

We chose a current research assignment, using a comparatively simple energy system model and a reduced scenario frame as case study. The regional association of the German green political party *Bündnis 90/Die Grünen* commissioned this research study in order to assess the impact of the energy strategy 2030 [30] of the federal state Brandenburg. The main focus was the investigation of changes in the political and economic conditions regarding lignite utilisation and the fulfilment of CO₂ reduction targets. It is the first study based on an energy system optimisation model with different scenarios that used the fact sheets. The case study tries to follow the concept of open science by using an open source model, publishing results as open data, publishing of the study under an open license, and compiling data in fact sheets. We want to point out that the focus of the paper is to analyse if the available tools that are used for publishing the case study can fulfil the requirements of the *transparency checklist*. We don't aim at assessing the study itself.

The approach of the case study is to build a model of the local energy system with regard to heat and electricity demand and generation. It is based on the *open energy modelling framework* (oemof) [31,32] and is called *oemof app Berlin Brandenburg* (oemof_abb). The model is hosted and publicly available at *GitHub* under the GPL-3.0 license [24].

Different types of heat and power generation, the projected energy consumption and the expected export of electrical energy are taken into account to determine load flows in and between the five subregions and the surrounding export regions on an hourly basis for an entire year. The utilisation of the existing grid as well as of the existing power plants and the carbon dioxide emissions, were analysed in three scenarios in order to examine the viability of the energy strategy. The final report aims to bridge the gap between a technical documentation, simple comprehension for non-experts, clear recommendations for action, and transparency. Links to the fact sheets, the technical documentation, and to the data if published are also available on the project website [33] and in the published final report [22].

3. Results

Evaluating the *transparency checklist* and applying it to the introduced case study lead to two additional sorts of categorisation of the questions. The first is the already mentioned differentiation between questions related to frameworks, models, or the different scenarios in order to avoid redundant information. The second categorisation is a differentiation into general *transparency*, *reproducibility*, and *quality* related questions. General transparency includes facts that provide information on the background and general framework of the investigation like name of authors and source of funding (e.g., 1.1.1 “Who are the ESS authors and for which institution(s) do they work?”). Reproducibility applies to documentation and measures that are necessary in order to reproduce the work and to achieve the same results and similar conclusions. This concerns both the re-implementation by the initial authors but especially an independent review (e.g., 4.12.1 “What is the input and output data of the model exercise?”). In contrast, quality-related questions include those questions which evaluate the quality of assumptions, equations, findings, and the overall approach (e.g., 6.19.3 “How far can the recommendations be differentiated?”). Especially this last differentiation seems important because transparency and reproducibility of a model or scenario simulation does not mean that its quality is high. In this context, quality describes a subjective assessment of whether the applied methods and tools are suitable to answer the respective research question. We want to point out that the classification into these three categories cannot be completely objective. While the assignment is quite clear on some questions (as with the examples chosen above), some questions are not clearly assignable.

The full list of questions with categorisation and the evaluation of our study is available in an online spreadsheet [34] and included in the annex. Table 1 shows the summarised results of the evaluation. The *Field* column comprises the original categories of the *transparency checklist*. The columns *T* (transparency), *R* (reproducibility), and *Q* (quality) declare how many questions have been assigned to each field respectively. The *Score* columns show how many of the questions of this category are answered sufficiently in the investigated study. The last column (*Total*) shows the total number of questions and the percentage of given answers. The result is that a total of 69% of the 45 questions were answered, whereas 14 questions could not be answered.

The evaluation shows that only one question concerning general transparency (1.1.2 “What are the authors' contributions in detail?”) could not be answered. The collaborative development of the model code can be tracked in the git version control of *GitHub* and each contribution can be allocated to a specific author. Other parts such as data processing and writing of the final report are not documented openly yet. The transparency score is 93%. Questions related to reproducibility are mainly addressing the involved data. Three of the eleven questions are not answered in the examined material, resulting

in a score of 73%. This is due to a lack of openness with regard to the output data and post-processing (corresponding questions of the checklist: 14.1 “Where can one find the numerical values (output) of the model?”, 16.1 “Are the presented results directly taken from the models' output or are they modified?”, and 16.2 “Are additional assumptions applied for this modification?”) [1]. Quality-related questions are only answered in part (47%). Most of these questions address the issues assumptions, uncertainties, and validation of results and recommendations (e.g., 7.1 “How do you deal with the uncertain factor you have identified?” and 19.3 “How far can the recommendations be differentiated?”).

If we look more closely at the relevant material to answer the questions of the *transparency checklist*, it can be seen that more than half (53%) of the answers come from the fact sheets. The rest of the material (final report, glossary, and *GitHub*) can only help to answer 16% while 31% remain unanswered. This analysis shows that the fact sheets are a suitable tool to complement a final report. Especially if the model is proprietary and not available to others.

4. Conclusion and outlook

By applying the *transparency checklist* to the published materials of the case study with an additional categorisation of the questions, we can evaluate the status-quo of transparency and reproducibility of the selected case study. By assigning and analysing the questions we come to a combined score of 83%. The analysis shows that the fact sheets are a suitable tool to record the most important information and further provide other useful functions like predefined answers and filters. In future, solutions for issues of documenting assumptions, uncertainties, and validation must be supplemented. The scenario and model fact sheets can be supplemented by additional fields. Though, the characterisation and implementation of quality criteria of the transparency checklist is far more difficult than those classified as transparency or reproducibility and will need additional evaluation and discussion.

With regard to the case study, all output data should be published online. It should be ensured that an appropriate license is chosen to make this data usable for others without copyright infringement. It is also important to create accompanying metadata to increase the traceability and understanding of the data and the applied post-processing. When choosing an open license, we suggest an import into an online database. The OEDB was developed to provide a collaborative database where raw data and processed data can be published under open licenses. Using it for a simple scenario, like the investigated case study, served the expectations. Even if the model is open source, the used data usually cannot be found in one place. Endogenous data appears only in the model and is not stored with the model data. This can be avoided by linking endogenous data in the corresponding fact sheet. Another unsolved problem in data management is referencing every value (every single cell from a table) to its primary source. A process intended to solve this problem for large data sets requires a higher degree of automation and improvements must contain both the necessary functionalities to link to different types of documents and ensure a practical application.

A closer look at the unanswered questions reveals a weakness in the adequate documentation of the data processing. For the reproducibility

Table 2
Entries and description of the scenario log.

Entry	Description
id*	Serial number, unique identifier
version	Software version number
action	Type of action or data flow
path	Database or file path
source	Name of the script or programme
comment	Additional information
user_name*	Name of the database user
timestamp*	Date and time
metadata*	A copy of the metadata if available

of complex studies with data pre-processing and data post-processing, even a publication of a final report, resulting data and model code is not sufficient. Without knowledge of the exact sequence of operations and actions performed (especially manual interventions), reconstruction is difficult or even impossible. For this application, we developed a *scenario log* which is based on the idea of the well-known analogue laboratory notebook as organisational tool to record different kinds of actions from multiple users and models also referred to by Davison [13]. The log records work steps and data flows in a database table or file (see grey arrows in Fig. 1). As shown in the figure, the *scenario log* supplements the fact sheets and adds valuable and detailed information about the data flow. Each time a function, script or program is executed, an entry is generated. The output is a log file with information of each data processing step (pre-processing and post-processing). Table 2 lists and describes the information collected in each entry. Entries marked with (*) are obtained from the system and filled in automatically. The implemented functions aim at high automation while following the basic principles of good scientific practice. Future work will include the application of the *scenario log* to different software applications used in energy system modelling and evaluating the transparency thus achieved.

We conclude that supplementing a final report or study with the presented fact sheets can improve good scientific practice significantly. The evaluation of the *transparency checklist* underlines the importance of a self-assessment and, for the first time, provides numbers for a selected case study. The objective is to compile a tool-box and applicable templates and evaluate its impacts for researchers who work with energy system analysis. This should cover different areas such as filling out fact sheets, publication of accompanying materials (with open licenses) and new ideas like the introduced *scenario log*. Opening up the research by increasing the transparency and reproducibility can increase quality and, thereby, hopefully enrich the insights obtained by energy policy-makers.

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Appendix A. Transparency checklist evaluation

Transparency Checklist			Case study (oemof_abb)			
ID	Field	Transparency question	Type	Answer	Material	Factsheet
1.1.1	General Information	Who are the ESS authors and for which institution(s) do they work?	T	y	FS	
1.1.2	General Information	In case of a collaborative ESS, what are the authors' contributions in detail?	T	n		
1.2.1	General Information	Who are the costumers requesting the study?	T	y	FS	SFS
1.2.2	General Information	Is there external funding? If yes, what is the source and to which proposal does it refer?	T	y	FS	SFS
1.2.3	General Information	What is the purpose (hypothesis) and research question of the study?	Q	y	EB	
1.2.4	General Information	What is different in comparison to the current state of research?	Q	y	EB	
1.3.1	General Information	How are key terms used in the study's context?	T	y	Glossary	
1.3.2	General Information	Where are key terms defined?	T	y	Glossary	
2.4.1	Empirical data	What are the sources of empirical data?	R	y	FS	SFS
2.5.1	Empirical data	Are empirical data used directly as model input or are data pre-processed?	R	y	FS	SFS
2.5.2	Empirical data	How is the characteristic of the empirical data adapted to the input requirements of the model(s)?	Q	y	FS	SFS
3.6.1	Assumptions	What are the (main) uncertain factors and corresponding assumptions (quantitative and qualitative)?	T	y	FS	MFS
3.6.2	Assumptions	Which uncertain factors are explicitly considered in the study?	R	y	EB	
3.7.1	Assumptions	How do you deal with the uncertain factor you have identified?	Q	n		
3.7.2	Assumptions	Which (alternative) development paths are assumed for the uncertain factors?	Q	n		
3.7.3	Assumptions	What are the sources of the chosen development paths?	R	y	EB	
3.7.4	Assumptions	Why and how are individual values chosen from a bandwidth of possible values?	Q	n		
3.8.1	Assumptions	What narrative description of scenarios is used which highlights the main scenario characteristics and dynamics?	T	y	FS	SFS
3.8.2	Assumptions	What is the relationship between the key driving forces?	T	y	FS	SFS
3.8.3	Assumptions	Which method is used to construct the storyline(s)?	Q	y	FS	SFS
3.8.4	Assumptions	Which normative assumptions are included in the storylines?	Q	y	FS	SFS
3.9.1	Assumptions	For the mentioned example in the section ' Empirical data ': The pre-processing is done by splitting up the national energy demand by population density. The assumption related to this is that the energy demand is proportionally distributed to the population density.	Q	n		
4.10.1	Model exercise	Which kind of modeling approach is used?	T	y	FS	MFS
4.10.2	Model exercise	What is the geographical coverage of the model?	T	y	FS	MFS
4.10.3	Model exercise	What temporal resolution and time horizon uses the model?	T	y	FS	MFS
4.10.4	Model exercise	Which sector is addressed by the model?	T	y	FS	MFS
4.10.5	Model exercise	How does the model deal with uncertainties?	Q	y	FS	MFS
4.11.1	Model exercise	What are the main specific characteristics (strengths and weaknesses) of this model regarding the purpose of the recommendation?	Q	n		
4.11.2	Model exercise	What are the new equations or essential equations?	T	y	FS	MFS
4.12.1	Model exercise	What is the input and output data of the model exercise?	R	y	FS	MFS
4.12.2	Model exercise	Does the model exercise include several models? If so, which data do these models exchange?	R	y	FS	MFS
4.13.1	Model exercise	Is there a complete documentation of the model available?	R	y	FS	MFS
4.13.2	Model exercise	Where are the units and symbols used in the equations documented?	T	y	FS	MFS
4.13.3	Model exercise	Is the model's source code accessible?	R	y	GitHub	
4.14.1	Model exercise	Where can one find the numerical values (output) of the model?	R	n		
4.15.1	Model exercise	What kind of validation method is used?	Q	y	FS	SFS
5.16.1	Results	Are the presented results directly taken from the models' output or are they modified?	R	n		
5.16.2	Results	Are additional assumptions applied for this modification?	R	n		
5.17.1	Results	How sensitive are the model results to parameter values variations?	Q	n		
5.18.1	Results	Are the model results within the expected deviation compared to commensurable models?	Q	y	FS	SFS
6.19.1	Conclusions and Recommendations	How do specific recommendations correspond to the results (e.g. output value or interpretation)?	Q	y	FS	SFS
6.19.2	Conclusions and Recommendations	How do results of the model exercise support normative recommendations with respect to the assumptions?	Q	n		
6.19.3	Conclusions and Recommendations	How far can the recommendations be differentiated?	Q	n		
6.20.1	Conclusions and Recommendations	Which normative assumptions are considered for deriving recommendations?	Q	n		
6.20.2	Conclusions and Recommendations	How reliable are the results due to the uncertainty of the assumptions and the modeling (e.g. system boundaries, model simplifications)?	Q	n		

FFS Framework Fact Sheet
MFS Model Fact Sheet
SFS Scenario Fact Sheet
EB Final report

References

- [1] K.-K. Cao, F. Cebulla, J.J.G. Vilchez, B. Mousavi, S. Prehofer, Raising awareness in model-based energy scenario studies—a transparency checklist, *Energy Sustain. Soc.* 6 (2016), <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-016-0090-z>.
- [2] C. Dieckhoff, H.-J. Appelrath, M. Fishedick, A. Grunwald, F. Höffler, C. Mayer, W. Weimer-Jehle, *Schriftenreihe Energiesysteme der Zukunft, Zur Interpretation von Energieszenarien*, Deutsche Akademie der Technikwissenschaften e. V., München, 2014.
- [3] Analysing Transition Planning and Systemic Energy Planning tools for the Implementation of the Energy Technology Information System (ATEsT), (2013) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <http://www.cres.gr/atest/>.
- [4] T. Koljonen, A. Leinonen, N. Wessberg, L. Sokka, A. Eerola, E. Pursiheimo, ATEsT: D6.1 Suggestions for Tools and Methodologies Development to Support SetPlan Implementation, (2012) <http://www.cres.gr/atest/pdf/D.6.1-Tools-and-Methodologies-Development.pdf>.
- [5] G.8 Science Ministers, G8 Science Ministers Statement London UK, (12 June 2013) <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/g8-science-ministers-statement-london-12-june-2013>.
- [6] European Commission, European Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP), (2017) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=open-science-policy-platform>.
- [7] European Commission, H2020 Programme: AGA – Annotated Model Grant Agreement, (2017) Version 4.1 (26 October 2017) http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf.
- [8] Forschungsnetzwerk Energiesystemanalyse, (2015) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <https://www.forschungsnetzwerke-energie.de/systemanalyse>.
- [9] Energy Modelling Platform for Europe 2017 (EMP-E), (2017) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <http://www.reeem.org/index.php/event/european-modelling-platform-for-europe-emp-e-2017-in-brussels/>.
- [10] Open Energy Modelling Initiative (openmod), (2018) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <http://openmod-initiative.org/>.
- [11] Openmod manifesto, (2018) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <http://openmod-initiative.org/manifesto.html>.
- [12] European Commission, Infrastructure for spatial information in the European community (INSPIRE), Accessed: 2018-01-18, 2018. <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/>.
- [13] A. Davison, Automated capture of experiment context for easier reproducibility in computational research, *Comput. Sci. Eng.* 14 (2012) 48–56, <https://doi.org/10.1109/mcse.2012.41>.
- [14] K. Hinsin, ActivePapers: a Platform for Publishing and Archiving Computer-aided Research, (2015), <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.5773.3> F1000Research.
- [15] C. Boettiger, An introduction to Docker for reproducible research, *ACM SIGOPS - Oper. Syst. Rev.* 49 (2015) 71–79, <https://doi.org/10.1145/2723872.2723882>.
- [16] V. Curcin, M. Ghanem, Scientific workflow systems - can one size fit all? 2008 Cairo International Biomedical Engineering Conference, IEEE, 2008, , <https://doi.org/10.1109/cibec.2008.4786077>.
- [17] S. Pfenninger, Energy scientists must show their workings, *Nature* 542 (2017), <https://doi.org/10.1038/542393a> 393–393.
- [18] Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), *Sicherung Guter Wissenschaftlicher Praxis*, Wiley-VCH, 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527679188.oth1>.
- [19] Open Electricity Grid Optimization (open_eGo), (2018) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <https://openegoproject.wordpress.com/>.
- [20] Open Feed-in time Series Based on a Renewable energy database (open_FRED), (2018) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <https://openfredproject.wordpress.com/>.
- [21] Reem Energy Systems Modelling Project, (2018) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <http://www.reeem.org/>.
- [22] E. Gaudchau, B. Müller, J. Twele, *Untersuchung der Energiestrategie Brandenburgs*, (2017) http://rl-institut.de/wp-content/publications/20170306_Gruene_Studie_BB/Untersuchungen_zur_Energiestrategie_2030.pdf.
- [23] OpenEnergyDatabase (OEDB), (2018) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <http://oep.iks.cs.ovgu.de/dataedit/>.
- [24] Oemof Application Berlin Brandenburg (oemof_abb), (2017) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <https://github.com/rl-institut/appBBB>.
- [25] Model Fact Sheet: oemof_abb, (2017) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <http://oep.iks.cs.ovgu.de/factsheets/models/32/>.
- [26] OpenEnergyPlatform (OEP), (2018) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <http://oep.iks.cs.ovgu.de/>.
- [27] Openmod Glossary, (2018) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <https://wiki.openmod-initiative.org/wiki/Category:Glossary>.
- [28] Openmod wiki, (2018) Accessed: 2018-01-18 https://wiki.openmod-initiative.org/wiki/Main_Page.
- [29] EnArgus, (2018) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <https://www.enargus.de/>.
- [30] Ministerium für Wirtschaft und Europaangelegenheiten des Landes Brandenburg, *Energiestrategie 2030 Brandenburg*, (2012) http://mwe.brandenburg.de/media/bb1.a.3814.de/Energiestrategie2030_2012.pdf.
- [31] Oemof Developer Group, *Open Energy Modelling Framework (oemof) - a Modular Open Source Framework to Model Energy Supply Systems*. Version v0.1.4, (2017), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.438676>.
- [32] S. Hilpert, C. Kaldemeyer, U. Krien, S. Günther, C. Wingenbach, G. Plessmann, *The Open Energy Modelling Framework (Oemof) - a Novel Approach in Energy System Modelling* [preprint], (2017), <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints201706.0093.v1> Preprints 2017.
- [33] *Untersuchung der energiestrategie brandenburgs*, (2018) Accessed: 2018-01-18 <http://rl-institut.de/untersuchungen-zur-energiestrategie-brandenburgs/>.
- [34] Checklist evaluation per category, (2017) Accessed: 2018-01-18 https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1E3JA8_QtpTBk99DcByO3vzk4mEZ-9u9p6GQJXmweRik/edit?usp=sharing.